

Ottawa NWR Project, Lucas County (41.63663, -83.21500)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Ottawa NWR Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally by adding water to wetland pools in the fall and draining them in the spring. Water was fully removed from the southern half of the Project (MS5) from May to September of 2024 for dike maintenance and water level control structures (WLCSs) were kept closed, isolating the permanently inundated Pool 3 and further restricting nutrient filtration opportunity.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. This Project has 586 acres of restored wetland, and its hydrologic features consist of a northern portion (Pool 3) and a southern portion (MS5), separated by Veler Road and its adjacent ditch. Ditch water flows west to east and can enter the northern and southern portions of the wetland complex through WLCSs. Water is released back into Veler Ditch or out into Crane Creek (ultimately outflowing directly to Lake Erie) during overflow events or in instances where water level is higher in the wetlands and the WLCS gates are opened. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an overflow event where water flows between the wetland units and Veler Ditch after WLCSs are opened.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Promote increased nutrient filtration opportunity by “cycling” nutrient-rich water from the source (i.e., Veler Ditch) through the wetland once or a few times per year, especially during the spring when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in Lake Erie.

As typical management activities resume following 2024 construction, different nutrient retention patterns may emerge, though the tradeoffs between habitat- and nutrient-driven water level management will remain. More accurate nutrient retention estimates for future years can be facilitated by prompt notification of WLCS actions allowing timely sampling of hydrologic events.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.